

METHOD OF TEACHING ENGLISH FOR ESP STUDENTS**Abdullayeva Nabiya Idrisovna**

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Abstract. *In this article the right methods of teaching English for students of technical institutes. Specified teaching methods are mostly discussed in this article.*

Key words: *Engineering, Engineering vocabulary, abbreviations, troubleshooting, Supervision, role-play, equipment and tools*

МЕТОД ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ ESP

Аннотация. *В этой статье правильные методы обучения английскому языку для студентов технических институтов. Указанные методы обучения в основном обсуждаются в этой статье.*

Ключевые слова: *Инженерия, Инженерный словарь, сокращения, устранение неполадок, Наблюдение, ролевая игра, оборудование и инструменты*

In an increasingly diverse, global economy, having a language in common greatly facilitates cross-cultural communication between people from different regions and nations. The English language is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world, second only to Mandarin. English being a widely-spoken language throughout the world is only one of the many advantages of learning the language.

The method of teaching foreign languages is a system of knowledge about the laws of the process of teaching a foreign language and the ways to influence this process in order to optimize it. Teaching method foreign language opens and substantiates the laws of foreign language teaching. Historically, there were two functionally different methods: General and private methods. The General technique, as a rule, is devoted to the study of the laws and features of the process of learning a foreign language, regardless of what foreign language in question. Thus, the principles of selection of educational material, the ratio of oral and written speech at different stages of the lesson, etc. they will be the same for any of the Western European languages studied in secondary schools of our country in equivalent conditions of education.[2, с. 610]

English is an international language, so learning English has several advantages. Firstly, we can get very good jobs easily with companies and non-government organization. Secondly, we can communicate with people all over the world in order we can understand each other very well. We can understand their cultures. Thirdly, if we are students, we need to research to improve our documents from the internet or libraries. In fact, most of the documents are written in English. Finally, learning English is really important to us in the modern world. These days if

we don't know English, we won't have a job. It is rather difficult to decide what English to teach to engineers. First of all, "engineer" has two rather distinct meanings, one of which is close to "technician" or "mechanic" (e.g. a photocopier repair engineer) and another which is closer to "designer". The needs of these two groups are likely to be different, but there are also people whose jobs and training fall somewhere in the middle. Another complication is that English for Engineers courses are also often for people still in full-time education, meaning no one has any idea which kind of job those people might end up in. Then there are the numerous different kinds of engineer (marine engineer, architectural engineer, genetic engineer, etc) with wildly different fields of work and very specialist vocabulary...

Having said all that, engineers tend to be interested in technical topics even if they have little relation to their own specialization, and technical topics also tend to bring up language that can be used to describe other kinds of engineering. There are also things that most kinds of engineers need to be able to understand, including:

- Abbreviations
- Adjectives, e.g. positive ones like "reliable" and negative ones like "rusty"
- Consequences/ Cause and effect
- Countable and uncountable nouns
- Dimensions, plus other units of measurement like pressures and temperatures and other numbers
- Directions, e.g. "vertical" and "anticlockwise"
- Equipment and tools
- Language to describe health and safety requirements, e.g. modal verbs
- Manuals
- Materials
- Opposites, e.g. "loose"/ "tight" and "plug in"/ "unplug"
- Other parts of speech, e.g. "loose"/ "loosen" and "wide"/ "width"
- Parts of things, e.g. leg of a chair/ Components and how they are put together
- Positions, e.g. "in the top left corner"
- Presentations, e.g. of a design or to explain an engineering failure
- Processes, e.g. "First of all" and "After that"
- Reports
- Shapes
- Talking about projects, e.g. planning and progress checks
- Things that engineers do, e.g. "check" and "measure"

- Things that machines and devices do and have done to them, e.g. “pivot” and “break down”
- Troubleshooting conversations, e.g. helpdesk phone calls and using “enough” and “too”
- Words which are always plural, e.g. “scissors”, “overalls”, “premises”, “tweezers”, “pincers” and “pliers”
- Words which have different general and technical meanings

There will also be some differences between the grammar syllabus of English for engineering and some other ESP courses, for example putting passive tenses earlier in this kind of course, covering the zero conditional long before the first and second conditional, and covering imperatives (pretty much useless for most General English courses). Making uncountable things countable with words like “a piece of...” and “a tube of...” is also likely to be important.

You’ll need to find out which kinds of language from the list above and which specific examples (e.g. which verbs would describe what they do) they need, by finding out more about the students before you meet them, through a needs analysis or by reading up about their industry and job.

Engineering vocabulary can be presented and practiced all the usual TEFL ways such as trying to make true sentences about your partner using one or more words on the list, Pictionary, miming, Taboo, and the definitions game. Because suitable things like “spanner” and “spring” can vary a lot (making them difficult to describe, draw etc), you might want to be more specific and give them “bed spring” and “adjustable spanner”.

Of those typical vocabulary games, the Definitions Game (asking students to describe the thing they are thinking of without mentioning any part of its name until their partner guesses what it is) is the most language intensive. You can add practice of other things that they need from the list above to the definitions game by giving them suggested language to describe things with, e.g. shapes, dimensions, materials, adjectives, actions that those things do, and actions that are done to those things. You can also ask them to stick to just one of those categories as long as possible, e.g. using three or four adjectives before they move onto other kinds of description. A version of this that I use a lot is called the Dimensions Guessing Game and consists of the person thinking of an object such as “gear lever” and describing its weight, diameter, length etc until their partner guesses. They could also be given dimensions of actual objects such as an iPad and the world’s biggest cargo ship to read out to their partner until they guess what is being described.

A similar game which combines numbers practice with lots of suitable vocabulary is a Numbers Trivia Guessing Game. One student asks their partner(s) to guess a number that they

have on their worksheet, e.g. “How much does the metal in the Eiffel Tower weigh?” They give clues like “much heavier” and “a tiny bit lighter” until their partner guesses the exact amount.

An activity which combines many more categories of vocabulary is a List Dictation. The teacher reads out a list of words until the students guess that the category is 3D shapes, man-made materials, or any of the categories above. They can then label the same categories on a worksheet and test each other in pairs or small groups. It is also possible to score points, with points off for wrong guesses. Perhaps before or after the List Dictation game, students can also be asked to brainstorm vocabulary into categories like those near the top of this article.

Particularly useful activities specific to some of the categories of language given at the top of the

Other good topics for speaking, listening and/ or reading (perhaps also with a writing homework) include:

- A Noble Prize for engineering
- Chindogu (“unuseless” Japanese inventions)
- Clever low-budget engineering, e.g. reuse of discarded machine parts
- Defining engineering, e.g. in contrast to design and science
- Education for engineers, e.g. how practical it should be and how much English is needed nowadays
- Engineering in particular countries, e.g. why the Germans respect engineers more than the British do or famous people and companies from one place
- Examples of bad engineering
- Extreme testing, e.g. crash tests
- Famous engineers
- How respected engineers are, e.g. how high status a job it is
- Inventions
- Inventors who had their ideas rejected by everyone, e.g. Dyson
- Kinds of engineer which are in demand or likely to be in the future
- Long term space missions, e.g. designing the interior of the spaceship or space station or thinking about amounts of things to take (good for countable and uncountable nouns)
- Moving from engineering to management
- New kinds of engineering
- Outsourcing of engineering jobs
- Patent law/ Patent disputes
- Predictions, e.g. wrong predictions from the past
- Robots

- Supervision of engineers by non-engineers, e.g. many of the Dilbert cartoons
- The history of engineering
- The world's biggest/ most successful engineering companies
- Tricky or amusing problems to solve (good for positive and negative words such as "corroded")
- Unusual uses of material, e.g. to make things more environmentally friendly

In conclusion, in technical institutes, it is advisable to teach English as specific purpose language rather than as a universal language. Advantages of teaching English to engineers are: first, they can freely express words and phrases related to their field in English, secondly, explain their fields using words and combinations, and thirdly, to plan future activities. They will not have difficulties to defend their further projects

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